

**MORPHOLOGICAL STUDY OF *CYPRIDOPSIS VIDUA*
(O.F.MÜLLER,1776)(CRUSTACEA :OSTRACODA) FROM BABYLON
GOVERNORATE IN IRAQ WITH SOME ECOLOGICAL OBSERVATIONS.**

Hanan Zwair

Department of Biology, College of Education for pure science, University of Karbala. Karbala
Iraq

hanan.mikhlif@uokerbala.edu.iq

ORCID <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2317-193X>

ABSTRACT

Thirteen females were collected during July from Babylon governorate(32° 30' 67, 59" N 44° 25' 45, 52 E"), *Cypridopsis vidua* is a species widely distributed in the aquatic environment. Males are not known in this species. Species diagnosed based on a number of diagnostic characteristics: Carapace with 4 dark green bands, Respiratory plate of Max with 4 filaments, LV overlaps RV ventrally and anteriorly.

Keywords: Crustacea, Ostracoda, Cyprididae, *Cypridopsis vidua*, Iraq

INTRODUCTION

Ostracoda is a small, bivalve crustacean found in marine, non-marine, and pond environments(Cohen & Morin 1990; Holmes & Chivas 2002). Podocopida includes Cypridoidea, Darwinuloidea, and Cytheroidea(Thorp, 2015)

The most common families in freshwater are Cyprididae(1000 species) and Candonidae (550 species) (Martens et al. 2007). Where they are found in the bottom of the water and on the surfaces and roots of aquatic plants (Suen & Gillett-Kaufman, 2021). *Cypridopsis* has a long geological record extending from the Lower Permian to recent (Swain 1976)

Cypridopsis vidua is a widespread species in all freshwater habitats. Members of this species feed on aquatic plants and a combination of algae (Roca *et al.* 1993). Also feed on plants and pollen, fungi, protozoans, fallen leaves, rotifers, nematodes, oligochaetes, cladocerans, copepods, chironomids, mosquito larvae, gastropod larvae, fish fry, amphibian eggs, dead animals, including Ostracoda (Gray *et al.*, 2010; Smith and Delorme, 2010; Ottonello and Romano, 2011; Rossi *et al.*, 2011).

A study by Smith *et al.* 2018 showed that *Cypridopsis vidua* exists for short periods in rice fields.

Cypridopsis vidua is one of the active swimmers and prefers large and small permanent bodies of water rich in plants. (Mbahinzireki *et al.* 1991). It is also found in temporary environments such as springs, ponds, and wells. (Roca *et al.*1993) (Danielopol *et al.* 1993). It can survive in environments with 8% salinity (Hiller, 1972). Furthermore, it can withstand the lack of oxygen in water (Danielopol, 1991). This species was also found in the rectum of the frog (Lowndes, 1930)

This species produces two generations per year, the first larvae appearing in the spring and reaching sexual maturity from June to July. The second larval role appears in August; Maturation

occurs in September and October (Corfu; Stephanides 1948). The males have never been found (Vinyard 1979)

METHODS AND MATERIALS

During the study, 13 females were collected from Shat Al-Hilla, Babylon Governorate, in July 2010 (32° 30' 67, 59" N 44° 25' 45, 52 E") (Map.1)

By the zooplankton collection network. Samples were preserved in 70% ethanol. After this, the dissecting process takes place in two main steps: the first is to separate the valves and the soft parts, and the second is to dissect the soft parts. The separation is done using dissection needles. The valves are placed on a special slide, and the soft parts are fixed with glycerine, dividing the body into anterior and posterior. The anterior includes A1, A2, Md, Mx1 T1, and the posterior includes the thoracic legs T2, T3, and the caudal rami (Namiotko et al. 2011). Diagnosis of species is based on the following taxonomic keys and research: Henderson (1990), Meisch (2000), Victor (2004), Fuhrmann (2012), Higuti & Martens (2020). AlAsady, H. S. and Aldaamy H.Z.M (2009), Aldaamy H.Z.M.(2014)

Map(1) Study area

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Systematic

Phylum Arthropoda

Subphylum Crustacea

Class Ostracoda

Order Podocopida

Family Cyprididae

Genus *Cypridopsis*

Species *Cypridopsis vidua*

Genus *Cypridopsis* Brady, 1867

1867 *Cypridopsis* Brady, Intell.Obs. 12(2):117.- Type species: *Cypris vidua* Müller, 1776 (designated by Brady & Nonman 1889 and Sars 1889).

Carapace ovate in both dorsal and lateral views; LV overlaps RV ventrally and longer than RV.A2 natatory setae well developed, reduced in some species. Maxilliped: Respiratory plate with 1 to 5 setae. genital fold of female with a chitinous plate. Uropodal triangular.

Species *Cypridopsis vidua*

1776 *Cypris vidua* O.F. Müller, Zool. Danicae Proder.:199

Carapace: (Fig.1)

Ovate in both dorsal and lateral views .Eyes fused. L 0.62mm ,W 0.48 .LV slightly longer than RV and slightly overlaps RV. Colour: yellowish with 4 dark green bands, covered with small hairs and pits.

Right and Left Valve: (Fig.1)

LV and R V similar in shape and structure, triangular, anterior margin broader than posterior. covered with Hairs. Adductor muscle scars eight ,variably arranged .

First Antenna: (Fig.1)

Basal bearing with four setae, third with one short seta, fourth and fifth each one with a single long seta, sixth with four setae, terminal with five long setae.

Second Antenna: (Fig.1)

Basal segment bearing one seta, Second bearing 3 setae. Endopod: first bearing a short sensory and a plumose seta. Exopod reduced to small lobe with one long and another short seta. Ventral covered with small hairs .Dorsal with(5+1) natatory setae extending beyond tips of terminal claws. Terminal bearing five equal claws and three setae.

Mandible: (Fig.2)

Basal segment elongate, base bearing five identical sharp teeth. Vibratory plate bearing four long identical filaments, setal group1 consists of two setae, group2 consist of four setae.

Maxilla: (Fig.2)

Maxillary palp consist of two segments, first bearing three setae, terminal bearing three setae Vibratory plate curved, with 14 marginal filaments and five basal setae. Third mastigatory process with two teeth bristles. .

First Thoracopod: (Fig.2)

Palp-like endopod ending with three setae .Mastigatory process ends with ten unequal setae.Vibratory plate with four filaments.

Second Thoracopod: (Fig.2)

Graduated in size, terminal segment is the smallest triangular and bearing one short seta and well-developed apical claw .

Third Thoracopod: (Fig.2)

Three-segmented, penultimate bear a long apical seta, terminal bearing small swollen one, and long lateral seta .

Uropod: (Fig.2)

Reduced, triangular with short lateral seta, ending with a flagellum.

ECOLOGICAL OBSERVATIONS

Teamperature of Water:29

Teamperature of Air:93

Electricity conductivity:0.50

pH:7.44

Salanity:0.032

(0.1mm —)

(0.01mm —)

Figure (1) *C. vidua* A; Adult female B; Right valve C; First Antenna D; Second Antenna.

Figure (2) *Cvidua* A; Mandible B; Maxilla C; 1st Thoracopod D; 2nd Tthoracopod E; 3rd Thoracopod F; Uropod.

References

- Aldaamy, H.Z.M.(2014). Description of a new species belongs to the genus *Cypridopsis* Brady 1867 (Crustacea, Ostracoda) from Karbalaa province with some ecological notes. *journal of kerbala university*, 12(3).
<https://iasj.net/iasj/download/6a374805d79d380a>
- AlAsady, H. S. and Aldaamy H.Z.M (2009). Description of a new species of the genus *Cypridopsis* Brady, 1867 (Crustacea: Ostracoda) from Iraq. *journal of kerbala university*, 7(3).
https://iraqjournals.com/?_action=article&au=1165609&_au=Hanan++amy
- Cohen, A.C. & Morin ,J.G. (1990). Patterns of reproduction in ostracodes: A review. *J. Crust. Biol.*, 10: 184-211.
- Danielopol ,D.L. (1991).Spatial distribution and dispersal of interstitial Crustacea in alluvial sediments of a backwater of the Danube at Vienna-Stygologia 6(2):97-110.
- Danielopol, D. L., Handl, M., & Yin, Y. (1993). Benthic ostracods in the pre-alpine deep lake Mondsee. Notes on their origin and distribution. In *International symposium on ostracoda. 11* (pp. 465-480).
- Fuhrmann, R. (2012). *Atlas quartärer und rezenter Ostrakoden Mitteleutschlands* (pp. 1-320). Altenburg: Naturkundliches Museum Mauritianum.
- Gray EP, Nunziata S, Snodgrass JW, Ownby DR, Havel JE.(2010). Predation on green frog eggs (*Rana clamitans*) by Ostracoda. *Copeia* 2010:452-456
- Henderson P.A. (1990). *Freshwater ostracods: keys and notes for the identification of the species*. London: Linnean Society.
- Hiller,D. (1972). untersuchungen zur biologia und zur Okologia limnischer Ostracoda aus der Umgebung von Hamburg- Archiv fire *Hydrobiologie*, Supplement-B and 40 (4): 400-497.
- Holmes, J.A. & Chivas A.R (Eds). (2002). *The Ostracoda. Applications in Quaternary research*. American Geophysical Union, Geophys. Monogr. 131, Washington DC: 313 pp.
- Higuti, J. & Martens, K. (2020). Class Ostracoda. In *Thorp and Covich's Freshwater Invertebrates* (pp. 631-661). Academic Press.
- Lowndes, A. G. (1930). Living ostracods in the rectum of a frog. *Nature*, 126(3190), 958-958.

- Mbahinzireki, G., Uiblein, F., & Winkler, H. (1991). Microhabitat selection of ostracods in relation to predation and food. *Hydrobiologia*, 222(2), 115-119.
- Martens K, Schön I, Meisch C, Horne DJ. 2008. Global diversity of ostracods (Ostracoda, Crustacea) in freshwater. *Hydrobiologia* 595: 185-193.
- Meish, C. (2000). Freshwater Ostracoda of western and central Europe. *Crustacea*.
Bronstein, Z. S. (1947). Ostracodes des eaux douces. *Institut Zoologique de l'Academie des Sciences de l'URSS, Nouvelle Serie*, 31, 339.
- Namiotko T., D.L. Danielopol & A. Baltana's. (2011). Soft body morphology, dissection and slide-preparation of Ostracoda: a primer. *Joannea Geologie und Palaontologie* 11: 327e343.
- Otonello D. and Romano A. (2011). Ostracoda and Amphibia in temporary ponds: who is the prey? Unexpected trophic relation in a Mediterranean freshwater habitat. *Aquatic Ecology*. 45:55-62.
- Roca JR, Baltanas A and Uiblein F. (1993). Adaptive responses in *Cypridopsis vidua* (Crustacea: Ostracoda) to food and shelter offered by a macrophyte (*Chara fragilis*). *Hydrobiologia* 262: 127-131.
- Rossi V.; Benassi G.; Belletti F. and Menozzi P. (2011). Colonization, population dynamics, predatory behaviour and cannibalism in *Heterocypris incongruens* (Crustacea: Ostracoda). *Journal of Limnology* . 70:102-108.
- Robin J. S; Dayou Z.(2017). Sukonthip SAVATENALINTON; Takahiro KAMIYA; Na yU.2018. A review of rice field ostracods (Crustacea) with a checklist of species. *J. Limnol.*, 2018; 77(1): 1-16. DOI: [10.4081/jlimnol.1648](https://doi.org/10.4081/jlimnol.1648)
- Smith AJ, Delorme LD, (2010). Ostracoda, p. 725-771. In: J.H. Thorp, A.P. Covich (eds.), *Ecology and classification of North American freshwater invertebrates*. Elsevier, London.
- Suen, C., & Gillett-Kaufman, J. L. (2021). Seed Shrimp, Mussel Shrimp (Freshwater Ostracods) scientific name:(Crustacea: Ostracoda: Podocopa): EENY-734/IN1260, 8/2019. *EDIS*, 2021(1), 3-3.
- Swain, F. M. (1976). Evolutionary development of *Cypridopsis* Ostracoda. *Abh. Verb. naturw. Ver. Hamburg, Suppl.* (NF) 18/19: 103-118.
- Thorp JH, Rogers DC. (2015). *Thorp and Covich's Freshwater Invertebrates*. 4th Edition. Elsevier Science, New York, NY. pp. 470-486.

Victor, R. (2004). Crustacea: ostracoda. yule, C. M & sen, YH (Eds). *Fresh water Invertebrates of the Malaysian Region. Academy of sciences Malaysia*, 225-252.

Vinyard, G. (1979). An ostracod (*Cypridopsis vidua*) can reduce predation from fish by resisting digestion. *American Midland Naturalist*, 188-190.